

IN INVESTIGATION OF THE TENSILE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR
OF IMPROVED CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

P.T.Curtis
Materials and Structures Dept.
Royal Aircraft Establishment
Farnborough, Hants
UK

ABSTRACT

Tensile static and fatigue tests, have been performed on eight unidirectional carbon fibre composite materials ranging from standard carbon fibre reinforced epoxy systems to high strain and intermediate modulus carbon fibres with toughened epoxy, bismaleimide and thermoplastic matrices. Tests were also performed on cross-plyed and +/-45 laminates.

Varying just the fibre type had little effect on unidirectional fatigue behaviour, however, varying the resin had a much greater effect with all the new tough matrices having poorer fatigue behaviour than the best standard epoxy system. When tested in cross-plyed form, the toughened epoxy system performed better in fatigue than the standard system, although the thermoplastic system still yielded poorer fatigue lives.

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing use is being made of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) because of their combination of high stiffness and high strength with low density and potentially low unit cost. The aerospace use of these materials to date has led to significant weight savings, although strain levels have been kept low, of the order of 0.3% to 0.4%. This has been partly because of conservatism on the part of designers and airworthiness authorities to the use of a radically new material but also because of reduced performance under

hot/wet conditions and in the presence of notches or impact damage.

In recent years manufacturers have sought to improve the mechanical properties of these 'first generation' composite materials based on standard high strength carbon fibres in epoxy resin matrices. Now carbon fibres with a breaking strain of 1.8% are widely available, all the major manufacturers offering products in this class. This improvement has been gained through the minimisation of internal defects and from further stretching to increase the polymer chain alignment and the subsequent orientation of the graphitic planes in the carbon fibres. The optimisation of fibre surface treatment to match these new fibres with the available resins appears to have received little attention.

Concurrently, resin manufacturers have sought to improve the performance of the composite epoxy matrix materials. The principle goal has been increased toughness without detriment to the high temperature properties, particularly in wet environments. Some manufacturers are also pursuing a different approach in which the base resin, generally epoxy in the past, has been exchanged for an alternative such as a bismaleimide. In modified form these offer the potential of increased toughness with some improvement in hot/wet performance, but at an increase in cost.

Alongside the developments in thermosetting composite matrices has been a surge of activity in continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics. This has resulted in manufacturers offering new systems claiming greatly improved toughness without the solvent susceptibility associated with many previous fibre reinforced thermoplastics.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and layups

Eight different materials were studied including four types of different carbon fibres and five different matrix materials, as listed in table 1. Laminates were moulded from preimpregnated sheets all 0.125 mm thick, except for system 5 where material supply forced the use of prepreg 0.16mm thick.

Balanced and symmetrical laminates were layed up in three different stacking sequences designated i, {04 }s, ii, {(+/-45,-/+45)2}s and iii, {0,90,90,0}s.

TABLE 1.
Materials studied.

System Number	Type of carbon fibre	Fibre Failure Strain %	Type of matrix
1.	Standard high strength fibre	1.2	Flow controlled standard epoxy with DICY cure
2.	Intermediate strain fibre	1.5	Flow controlled standard epoxy with DICY cure
3.	High failure strain fibre	1.7	Flow controlled standard epoxy with DICY cure
4.	Intermediate modulus fibre	1.5	Flow controlled standard epoxy with DICY cure
5.	Intermediate failure strain fibre	1.5	Standard DDS cured epoxy
6.	Intermediate modulus fibre	1.5	Toughened flow controlled epoxy
7.	Intermediate modulus fibre	1.5	Modified bismaleimide based resin
8.	Intermediate failure strain fibre	1.5	Semi-crystalline thermoplastic

Except for system 8, the laminates were cured in an autoclave to the manufacturers recommended cure schedules, usually to a temperature of approximately 170°C, then postcured as recommended. Some panels of the thermoplastic based system (8) were kindly supplied by the manufacturer. Other panels were moulded in-house at RAE Farnborough, in a hot press at a temperature of 380°C. The manufacturer recommended a minimum cooling rate of 10°C/min. which was not achievable in the equipment available and the panels were cooled at just 3°C/min. Fibre volume fractions were measured by the acid digestion technique, all values being between 56 and 62%. Where appropriate, measured strengths and stiffnesses were corrected to a volume fraction of 62% by assuming a linear relationship between test parameter and fibre volume fraction.

2.2 Test methods

Constant amplitude fatigue tests were performed in load

control on unidirectional, (0,90) and (+/-45) coupons. Sinusoidal loading at a constant frequency of 10Hz. was used except for the +/-45 layups which were tested at a constant average loading rate of 30kN/s (this is approximately equivalent to a stress rate of 750MPa/s). Forced cooling by a motorised fan was used to minimise any hysteresis heating effects in the materials. Damage development was studied in a few specimens using infra-red thermography during the fatigue tests and optical microscopy of sectioned coupons.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fatigue data is presented in the form of initial applied strain equivalent to the peak tensile stress versus log.cycles to failure, a form of S-N plot. This form of presentation is more informative, as has been observed by others [1], permitting easier comparison between materials for design purposes and making it easier to relate damage processes in the materials with applied strains. The strains were determined by dividing the peak stresses by the mean material moduli determined in static tests. For comparative purposes, the data was fitted to a function of the following form using a four parameter regression fit:-

$$s = a(c + n)^b + d$$

where s is strain, n is fatigue cycles and a, b, c and d are constants. The correlation coefficients for the fits to the experimental data were very good for fatigue work, all being in excess of 0.9 and many much higher.

3.1 Tests on unidirectional laminates

To interpret the fatigue behaviour of these new materials it is necessary first to establish the tensile fatigue failure process in unidirectional composite materials, something that is not well understood. Work has been done by Jamison et al [2,3] in which the progressive development of fibre breaks has been monitored but it is unlikely that the general degradation of the material is due entirely to fibre fracture. Work by others [4,5,6] has shown

Fig 1 Initial peak tensile strain (corresponding to applied peak stress) versus log cycles to failure for four unidirectional CFRP systems with the same standard epoxy matrix

Fig 2 Initial peak tensile strain (corresponding to applied peak stress) versus log cycles to failure for three unidirectional CFRP systems with the same high strain carbon fibre

resin cracking and interfacial damage initiating from individual fibre fractures and elsewhere in the composite. These lead to the development and growth of longitudinal splits parallel to fibres, which become quite extensive close to failure and result in the brush-like failures characteristic of unidirectional fibrous composites. The process of damage initiation is not clear, although fibre ends, as sites of high shear stress, have been observed by many workers to initiate resin damage. Apart from these, resin rich regions, general fibre volume fraction variation and fibre distortion could also induce local shear stresses in the resin and become sites for crack development and growth. Thus fatigue failures in fibrous composites are controlled principally by the resin and fibre/resin interface rather than the fibres, although if greater demands are put on the resin matrix through the use of high strain fibres then poorer fatigue properties may result. Consequently, for the same working strain, varying the resin would be expected to have a greater effect on fatigue behaviour than varying the fibres, although the latter could also result in interfacial changes which may induce behavioural differences. Generally, therefore, the unidirectional fatigue performance of composite materials should be a function of the incipient resin and interfacial damage and the susceptibility of the material to shear crack growth from these defects.

The latter stages of the process outlined above were apparent in this work, with longitudinal splits observed, in all materials tested in tensile fatigue. These grew and became quite extensive close to failure. Varying just the type of fibre, as shown in fig.1, was found to have little effect on the fatigue behaviour as would be expected if the failure process followed that outlined above. Some slight shifting of the S-N curves on the ordinate was observed, as might be expected for fibres with widely varying static failure strains. However, varying the resin type with the same fibrous reinforcement, as in figures 2 and 3, had a dramatic effect on the fatigue behaviour. The new tough matrices all had much poorer fatigue behaviour than the standard epoxy based systems, with large reductions in supportable strain with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles. In systems 5, 7 and 8 the fatigue strain had fallen to

Fig 3 Initial peak tensile strain (corresponding to applied peak stress) versus log cycles to failure for three unidirectional CFRP systems with the same intermediate modulus carbon fibre

Fig 4 Initial peak tensile strain (corresponding to applied peak stress) versus log cycles to failure for three 0, 90 cross-ply CFRP systems

approximately 0.7% at 10 million cycles, considerably less than the values around 1% for the standard materials (systems 1 and 2) which gave the best tensile fatigue behaviour.

The poorer tensile fatigue behaviour of the tough materials must be associated with the new resins or the fibre/matrix interface. Indeed some of the new systems have been found to be susceptible to longitudinal splitting during impact and in notched compression testing {7}. This was particularly noticeable in system 8, the tough thermoplastic based system, which had the poorest fatigue behaviour and which was found in static tests to be particularly susceptible to longitudinal splitting. The poorer fatigue performance of the toughened thermoset systems may be partly explained by a greater tendency to longitudinal splitting, but perhaps the principal reason was poorer shear fatigue behaviour than in the standard materials. This could be assessed by carrying out fatigue tests on +/-45 layups from these systems, which were unfortunately not performed in this programme. At present it would be prudent for designers working with these new materials to avoid laminates with very high percentages of 0° fibres (perhaps greater than 80%) and to insist upon fatigue data being available for the layups being considered.

3.2 Tests on the 0,90 layup

The fatigue behaviour of the 0,90 layup for three systems (1,6,8) is presented in figure 4 in the form described above for the unidirectional material. The standard carbon fibre in the flow controlled epoxy resin had a fairly flat S-N curve, as observed by many researchers {4,5,8}. The toughened epoxy system (6) had better static performance than the standard system 1, and although the S-N curve was slightly steeper at long lifetimes it still had superior fatigue behaviour. As in the unidirectional material the thermoplastic based system had a steeper S-N curve, although the effect was slightly less severe than for the unidirectional case. Interestingly the fatigue failures of 0,90 coupons from system 8 were grouped, apart from one, into two distinct sets. The first all failed between 3000 and 20000 cycles, the second all ran out in excess of 10 million

cycles.

Longitudinal splitting along the 0° fibres was less of a problem than in the unidirectional material because of the lateral and shear constraint imposed by the 90° fibres. Therefore system 6, based on the toughened epoxy resin had a much improved fatigue behaviour (fig.4). Microstructural observation revealed the epoxy based systems developed both translaminar cracks across the 90° layers and delamination between layers, initiated mainly at the ends of the translaminar cracks (despite the greater interlaminar fracture toughness of the toughened epoxy system). This prevented the growth of the translaminar 90° layer cracks into the load bearing 0° layers. However, in the thermoplastic based system, delamination was greatly suppressed, so that delamination frequently did not form at the ends of the translaminar 90° cracks. This was particularly noticeable at high stresses, which permitted the translaminar cracks to fracture the load bearing 0° layers. At lower stresses delamination did form, over a large number of cycles, so that the S-N curve flattened out at around 0.7% strain. This also served to explain the distinct bimodal grouping of failures in this system.

3.3 Tests on the +/-45 layup

The fatigue behaviour of both +/- 45 materials was similar (fig.5), except for coupons from system 8 that had been cooled at the faster rate of $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$ after pressing, which had significantly improved fatigue lives. The damage in fatigued coupons from system 1 consisted of extensive delamination with much translaminar cracking, but in system 8 the damage was slightly different, there being extensive translaminar cracking, but little delamination. In this latter material the large interlaminar stresses were absorbed not by delamination but by shear within the layers, either by fibres kinking or by matrix shearing and fibre distortion.

Coupons cooled at the faster rate had significantly increased fatigue strength (and static strength). System 8 is based on a semi-crystalline thermoplastic [9], which when cooled slowly develops larger spherulites and a greater degree of crystallinity than when cooled more rapidly. This

Fig 5 Peak applied tensile stress versus log cycles to failure for ± 45 laminates from systems 1 and 8

difference in morphology must be influencing the behaviour of the ± 45 material. More work is in progress to attempt to understand the reasons for this behaviour.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Varying just the type of fibre was found to have little effect on the fatigue behaviour of the materials, although some slight shifting of the S-N curves on the ordinate was observed, as might be expected for fibres with widely varying static failure strains. However, varying the resin type with the same fibrous reinforcement, had a dramatic effect, the new tough matrices all having much poorer unidirectional fatigue behaviour than the best standard epoxy based systems, with large reductions in supportable strain with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles. When tested in cross-plyed form, the toughened epoxy system had superior fatigue behaviour to the standard epoxy composite, but the tough thermoplastic based material was still worse.

Should static design allowables be raised, fatigue behaviour may become more important than at present. Designers and airworthiness authorities, therefore, cannot afford to ignore the fatigue behaviour of these new tough materials in aerospace designs.

REFERENCES

1. Talreja, R., Fatigue of composite materials: damage mechanisms and fatigue life diagrams. *Proc.R.Soc.Lond.*, 1981, A.378, p461.
2. Reifsnider, K.L. and Jamison, R.D., Fracture of fatigue loaded composite laminates, *Int.J.Fatigue*, Oct 1982, p187.
3. Jamison, R.D., Schulte, K., Reifsnider, K.L. and Stinchcomb, W.W., Characterisation and analysis of damage mechanisms in tension-tension fatigue of graphite-epoxy laminates. 1984 ASTM STP836, p21-55.
4. Curtis, P.T. and Moore, B.B., A comparison of plain and double waisted coupons for static and fatigue testing of unidirectional GRP and CFRP. RAE TR82031, 1982.
5. Sturgeon, J.B., Rhodes, F.S. and Moore, B.B., The fatigue behaviour of a carbon fibre composite with laminate constructions of 0 , $0+/-45$ and $90+/-45$. RAE TR78031, 1978.
6. Barnard, P.M., Butler, R.J. and Curtis, P.T., Fatigue scatter of unidirectional glass epoxy; a fact or fiction, Proceedings of the third international conference on Composite structures, Paisley, Scotland, (1985).
7. Curtis, P.T., An investigation of the mechanical properties of improved carbon fibre composite materials. 1986, RAE TR86021.
8. Sturgeon, J.B. and Moore, B.B., The fatigue properties of 0 , $+/-45$, $0+/-45$, $90+/-45$ carbon fibre reinforced plastics, RAE TR76153, 1976.
9. Cogswell, F.N., Microstructure and properties of thermoplastic aromatic polymer composites. SAMPE quarterly, July 1983, p33.